

Supplementary material for the publication:

Line Tang Møllehave, Mia Klinten Grand, Margit Kriegbaum, Christen Lykkegaard Andersen, Bent Struer Lind, Nicolien Alien van Vliet, Diana van Heemst, Katrine Strandberg-Larsen: Maternal thyroid function in early pregnancy and offspring school performance and neurodevelopmental disorders, *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*, 2024; <https://doi.org/10.1210/clinem/dgae358>

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Supplementary Figure S1: Lexis diagram of the study population and ages for the school tests and lower age limits for definition of ADHD and ASD.

Supplementary Figure S2a: Number of TSH and fT4 measurements by gestational week in the populations analysed for school performance

TSH levels are defined as low (<0.1 mIU/l), normal (0.1-2.4 mIU/l), and high (>2.5 mIU/l)

fT4 levels are defined as low (<12.0 pmol/l), normal (12-18.9 pmol/l), and high (≥19 pmol/l)

Supplementary Figure S2b: Number of TSH and fT4 measurements by gestational in the populations analysed for neurodevelopmental disorders

TSH levels are defined as low (<0.1 mIU/l), normal (0.1-2.4 mIU/l), and high (>2.5 mIU/l)

fT4 levels are defined as low (<12.0 pmol/l), normal (12-18.9 pmol/l), and high (≥19 pmol/l)

Supplementary Figure S3: Differences in standardized test scores at the school tests according to the mean maternal level of TSH during the first trimester of pregnancy in women without and with a history of thyroid disorder. Data are presented as adjusted means with standard errors.

Supplementary Figure S4: Differences in standardized test scores at the school test according to the mean maternal level of TSH during GW 1-6 and GW 7-12. Data are presented as adjusted means with standard errors.

Supplementary Figure S5: Differences in standardized test scores at the school tests according to the mean maternal level of fT4 during the first trimester of pregnancy in women without and with a history of thyroid disorder. Data are presented as adjusted means with standard errors.

Supplementary Figure S6: Differences in standardized test scores at the school test according to the mean maternal level of fT4 during GW 1-6 and GW 7-12. Data are presented as adjusted means with standard errors.

